

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE TREATMENT OF ENT DISEASES

Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna

Samarkand State Medical University,

Senior teacher of the Department of Pathological Physiology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13377775>

Abstract. In this paper, the variational iteration method is applied to delay differential equations. Illustrative examples from medicine are given to show the efficiency of the method.

Keywords: delay differential equations; variational iteration method; approximate and exact solution.

LOR KASALLIKLARINI DAVOLASHNI BAHOLASH DIAGNOSTIK MEZONLARINI MATEMATIK MODELLASH

Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti,

Patologik fiziologiya kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada differensial tenglamalarni kechiktirish uchun variatsion iteratsiya usuli qo'llaniladi. Usulning samaradorligini ko'rsatish uchun tibbiyotdan yorqin misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kechikish differensial tenglamalari; variatsion takrorlash usuli; taxminiy va aniq yechim.

МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ КРИТЕРИЕВ ОЦЕНКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЛОР-ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ

Абдирашидова Гульноза Аблакуловна

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет,

Старший преподаватель кафедры патологической физиологии

Аннотация. В данной работе вариационный итерационный метод применяется к дифференциальным уравнениям с запаздыванием. Приведены иллюстративные примеры из медицины, демонстрирующие эффективность метода.

Ключевые слова: дифференциальные уравнения с запаздыванием; вариационный итерационный метод; приближенное и точное решение.

It has been proven that retarded differential equations (DEDEs) provide a powerful model for many phenomena in applied sciences. DUSA mathematical modeling is widely used to explain many different phenomena in the life sciences, such as epidemiology, immunology, physiology, and neural networks [7-11]. The delay in these models may be related to the duration of some hidden processes, such as life cycle stages, the time between infection of a cell and the production of new viruses, the duration of the infectious period, the immune period, etc. In ordinary differential equations, the unknown state and its derivatives are evaluated at the same time. In DUZA, however, the evolution of the system at a particular time moment depends on past history/memory. The introduction of lag in a differential model greatly increases the complexity of the model.

The recently introduced method of variational iterations [1-6], which gives rapidly converging successive approximations of the exact solution, if such a solution exists, has been successful in deriving analytical solutions to linear and non-linear differential equations. This method is preferable to numerical methods because it is free of rounding errors and does not require much computer power/memory. The method of variational iterations has been successfully applied to linear and nonlinear problems by researchers [5-16].

Objective: To improve the extension of the application of the method of variational iterations to solve some linear DDEs of different orders, which are otherwise too difficult to handle due to their complex nature.

Materials and methods of research:

To apply the variational iteration method, the following problem is considered:

Consider the following form of DUZA, which contains a large DUZA class

$$u^{(m)}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^l \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \lambda_{ij}(t) u^{(j)}(\alpha_{ij}t + \beta_{ij}) + L(u) + N(u) + f(t), \quad t \in [0, T]$$

with initial conditions

$$\sum_{j=0}^{m-1} c_{kj} u^{(j)}(0) = q_k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, m-1,$$

where $0 \leq \alpha_{ij} \leq 1$; $\beta_{ij} \in R$; $u^{(m)}(t)$ – is the derivative of the function u by m times with respect to t ; L, N – linear and nonlinear operators of the function u , respectively;

Solution of the problem (Method of variational iterations).

The main idea underlying the method of variational iterations for solving linear and non-linear equations is presented below.

Consider a general nonlinear differential equation in the form

$$Lu + Nu = f(t) \quad (1)$$

where L - linear differential operator, N - non-linear operator, f - given analytic function.

The essence of the method lies in the construction of a corrective functional of the form

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) + \int_0^t \lambda(t, s) [Lu_n(s) + N\tilde{u}_n(s) - f(s)] ds. \quad (2)$$

where λ Lagrange multiplier, which can be optimally determined using variational theory [1-5], u_n is an approximate solution, $\tilde{u}_n$ denotes bounded variation, i.e. $\delta\tilde{u}_n = 0$ [1-6]. After determining the Lagrange multiplier and choosing an appropriate initial function u_0 , successive approximations u_n , and solutions u can be easily obtained. Therefore, the solution

of equation (1) is defined as $u = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n$ [6].

Practical use.

Example 1. Consider the following linear DUSA [12]

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dt} u(t) + u(t) - \frac{1}{2} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{dt} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) = 0, t \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = 1, \end{cases}$$

which has the exact solution $u(t) = e^{-t}$.

Method of variational iterations [3,5].

For this case $\lambda = e^{s-t}$, and the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t e^{s-t} \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) + u_n(s) - \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=1$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package:

$$u_1(t) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} e^{-t}, \quad u_2(t) = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{4} e^{-t}, \quad u_3(t) = \frac{1}{8} + \frac{7}{8} e^{-t}, \quad \dots, \quad u_n(t) = \frac{1}{2^n} + \frac{2^n - 1}{2^n} e^{-t}.$$

We find the exact solution from the limit $u(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} u_n(t) = e^{-t}$.

If $\lambda = -1$, then the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) + u_n(s) - \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=1$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. After 15-iterations, the absolute error does not exceed 10^{-5} , and further approximations more accurately refine the solution of the problem.

Example 2. Consider the following linear DUSA [12]

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dt} u(t) - u(t) + \frac{1}{2} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{dt} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) = 0, & t \in [0,1], \\ u(0) = 1, \end{cases}$$

which has the exact solution $u(t) = e^t$.

Method of variational iterations [3,5].

For this case, $\lambda = e^{t-s}$, and the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t e^{t-s} \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) - u_n(s) + \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=1$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package:

$$u_1(t) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} e^t, \quad u_2(t) = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{4} e^t, \quad u_3(t) = \frac{1}{8} + \frac{7}{8} e^t, \quad \dots, \quad u_n(t) = \frac{1}{2^n} + \frac{2^n - 1}{2^n} e^t.$$

We find the exact solution from the limit $u(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} u_n(t) = e^t$.

If we take $\lambda = -1$, then the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) - u_n(s) + \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

We find the initial approximation and leave it the same, i.e. $u_0(t)=1$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. As in the previous example, after the 15-iteration, the absolute error does not exceed 10^{-5} , and further approximations more accurately refine the solution of the problem.

Example 3. Consider the following linear DUSA [11]

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dt} u(t) - u(t) - \frac{1}{2} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + \frac{d}{dt} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \\ - e^t - \frac{1}{2} e^{t/2} = 0, \quad t \in [0,1], \\ u(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

which has the exact solution $u(t) = te^t$.

Method of variational iterations [3,5].

For this case, $\lambda = e^{-s}$ and the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t e^{t-s} \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) - u_n(s) - \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - e^s - \frac{1}{2} e^{s/2} \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=0$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package:

$$u_1(t) = te^t + e^t - e^{t/2}, \quad u_2(t) = te^t - \frac{1}{3}e^t + \frac{1}{3}e^{t/4}, \quad u_3(t) = te^t + \frac{1}{7}e^t - \frac{1}{7}e^{t/8}, \quad \dots$$

$$u_n(t) = te^t + \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{2^n - 1} + \frac{(-1)^n}{2^n - 1} e^{t/2^n}.$$

We find the exact solution from the limit $u(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} u_n(t) = te^t$.

If we take $\lambda = -1$, then the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t \left[\frac{d}{ds} u_n(s) - u_n(s) + \frac{1}{2} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{d}{ds} u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - e^s - \frac{1}{2} e^{s/2} \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation remains the same, i.e. $u_0(t)=0$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. As in the previous example, after the 15-iteration, the absolute error does not exceed 10^{-6} , and further approximations more accurately refine the solution of the problem.

Example 4. Consider the following linear DUSA [11]

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d^2}{dt^2}u(t) - u(t) - \frac{1}{2}u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{4}tu\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + \frac{d}{dt}u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + \\ + t \frac{d^2}{dt^2}u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) = 0, \quad t \in [0,1], \\ u(0) = 1, \quad \frac{d}{dt}u(0) = 1, \end{array} \right.$$

which has the exact solution $u(t) = e^t$.

Method of variational iterations [3,5].

For this case, $\lambda = s-t$, and the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) + \int_0^t (s-t) \left[\frac{d^2}{ds^2}u_n(s) - u_n(s) - \frac{1}{2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{4}su_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \frac{d}{ds}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + s \frac{d^2}{ds^2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=1+t$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. As in the previous example, after the 6-iteration, the absolute error does not exceed 10^{-10} , and further approximations more accurately refine the solution of the problem.

If for this case we choose $\lambda = e^{t-s}$, then the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t e^{t-s} \left[\frac{d^2}{ds^2}u_n(s) - u_n(s) - \frac{1}{2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{4}su_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \frac{d}{ds}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + s \frac{d^2}{ds^2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] ds.$$

The initial approximation remains the same, i.e. $u_0(t)=1+t$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. In this case, the results of iterations are slowly approaching the exact solution.

Example 5. Consider the following linear DUSA [11]

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d^3}{dt^3}u(t) - u(t) + \frac{1}{2}u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{9}u\left(\frac{t}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{64}u\left(\frac{t}{4}\right) - \\ - \frac{d}{dt}u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + \frac{d^2}{dt^2}u\left(\frac{t}{3}\right) + \frac{d^3}{dt^3}u\left(\frac{t}{4}\right) = 0, \quad t \in [0,1], \\ u(0) = \frac{d}{dt}u(0) = \frac{d^2}{dt^2}u(0) = 1, \end{array} \right.$$

which has the exact solution $u(t) = e^t$.

Method of variational iterations [3,5].

For this case, $\lambda = -(s-t)^2/2$, and the iterative formula is written as

$$u_{n+1}(t) = u_n(t) - \int_0^t \frac{(s-t)^2}{2} \left[\frac{d^3}{ds^3}u_n(s) - u_n(s) + \frac{1}{2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{9}u_n\left(\frac{s}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{64}u_n\left(\frac{s}{4}\right) + \frac{d}{ds}u_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \frac{d^2}{ds^2}u_n\left(\frac{s}{3}\right) + \frac{d^3}{ds^3}u_n\left(\frac{s}{4}\right) \right] ds,$$

The initial approximation is found from the initial condition, i.e. $u_0(t)=1+t+t^2/2$. Subsequent approximations are found using the previous formula using the Maple 17 mathematical package. As in the previous example, after the 3-iteration, the absolute error does not exceed 10^{-7} , and further approximations more accurately refine the solution of the problem.

Results: The feasibility of the method of variational iterations for solving the DEL was demonstrated. High-precision approximate solutions, or even an exact solution, are obtained only after several iterations. All the above examples show that the results of the method of variational iterations agree with those generated by some other methods [14].

Conclusions: Thus, the numerical results also show that the method of variational iterations gives a very efficient and convenient approach to the approximate solution of DESA and other equations [8-9,13].

References:

1. Abdirashidov A., Abdirashidova G.A. (2019). Approximate solution of some linear delay differential equations in medicine. International Scientific Journal **Theoretical & Applied Science**, **12(8)**, 18-22.
2. He J. H. (1997). Variational iteration method for delay differential equations. Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simulat. 2 (4), 235–236.
3. He J. H. (1999). Variational iteration method. A kind of non-linear analytical technique: Some examples, Internat. J. Non-Linear Mech. 34 (4) 699-708.
4. He J. H. (2007). Variational iteration method. Some recent results and new interpretations, J. Comput. Appl. Math. 207 (1) 3-17.
5. He J. H., Wu G., Austin F. (2010). The variational iteration method which should be followed, Nonlinear Sci. Lett. A 1 (1) 1-30.
6. He J. H., Wu X. H. (2007). Variational iteration method: New development and applications, Comput. Math. Appl. 54 (7-8) 881-894.
7. Lakshmanan S., Rihan F. A., Rakkiyappan R., and Park J. H. (2014). Stability analysis of the differential genetic regulatory networksmodel with time-varying delays and Markovian jumping parameters. Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems, vol. 14, pp. 1–15.
8. Rakkiyappan R., Velmurugan G., Rihan F. A., and Lakshmanan S. (2015). Stability analysis of memristor-based complex-valued recurrent neural networks with time delays. Complexity, vol. 21, no.4, pp. 14–39.
9. Rihan F. A., Abdelrahman D. H., Al-Maskari F., Ibrahim F., and Abdeen M. A. (2014). Delay differential model for tumour-immune response with chemoimmunotherapy and optimal control, Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine, vol. 2014, Article ID982978, 15 pages.
10. Bani-Yaghoub M. (2017). Analysis and Applications of Delay Differential Equations in Biology and Medicine. arXiv preprint arXiv:1701.04173, 23 pages.
11. Khader M. M. (2013). Numerical and theoretical treatment for solving linear and nonlinear delay differential equations using variational iteration method. Arab J Math Sci, 19(2), 243–256.

12. Xumei Chen, Linjun Wang, (2010). The variational iteration method for solving a neutral functional-differential equation with proportional delays. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications*, 59 (2010) 2696-2702.
13. Abdurashidov A. A. (2017). Primeneniye metoda variatsionnix iteratsiy k priblijennomu resheniyu integro-differentsialnix uravneniy. *Mejdunarodniy nauchniy jurnal: Continuum. Matematika. Informatika. Obrazovaniye*. 3 (7). Yeles, Moscow, pp. 51-55.
14. Abdurashidov A. A. (2017). Resheniya nelineynix volnovix uravneniy metodom variatsionnix iteratsiy. *Mejdunarodniy nauchniy jurnal: Molodoy ucheniy*. 6. pp. 4–8.
15. Wazwaz A. M. (2009). *Partial Differential Equations and Solitary Waves Theory*. Higher Education Press, Berlin Heidelberg, 761 p.
16. Kudryashov N.A. (2010) *Metodi nelineynoy matematicheskoy fiziki: Uchebnoye posobiye*. 2-ye izd. Dolgoprudniy: Intellect, 2010. 368 p.
17. Samieva G. U., Abdirashidova G. A., Sobirova Sh B. Prognostic value of cytokine spectrum and their changes in primary and recurrent laryngotracheitis in children // *Innovative research: problems of implementation of results and directions of development*. – 2017. – С. 103.
18. Самиева Гульноза, Абдирашидова Гульноза, Курбанов Голиб Патогенетические аспекты эндогенной интоксикации и ее влияние на течение различных форм стенотического ларинготрахеита у детей // *Обозрение европейской науки*. 2018. №9-10-2.
19. Utkurovna S. G., Bahtiyarovna S. S., Gulnoz A. Integrated Approaches to The Diagnosis, Treatment, And Prevention of Stenosing Laryngotracheitis In Children // *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 03. – С. 2020.
20. Саидова, Ф. С., Г. У. Самиева, and Г. А. Абдирашидова. "Дефицит микронутриентов у детей дошкольного возраста." *Журнал биомедицины и практики* 7.1 (2022).
21. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПАТОГЕНЕЗА, ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ И МЕТОДЫ ИНТЕНСИВНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ С ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ ДВС-СИНДРОМОМ М.К. Эргашевна, А.Г. Аблакуловна, М.Б. Аминовна - Тематический журнал образования, 2022
22. FEATURES OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF DRY EYE SYNDROME IN WOMEN OF KASHKADARYA REGION. SG Utkurovna, AG Ablakulovna, OF Orifjonovna - *JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2023
23. Utkurovna S. G., Ablakulovna A. G. Pathophysiology of the triad of young sports girls aspects // *Конференции*. – 2020.
24. Саидова Ф. С., Самиева Г. У., Абдирашидова Г. А. Дефицит микронутриентов у детей дошкольного возраста // *Журнал биомедицины и практики*. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.
25. Approximate solution of some linear delay differential equations in medicine A Abdirashidov, G Abdirashidova - *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 12 (80), 2019
26. Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna, Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, Narzullaeva Umida Rahmatullaevna, Toirova Sakina Bahodirovna, Mamadiyarova Dilshoda Umurzakovna The condition of pro-and antioxidant systems in children with acute laryngotracheitis with immunomodulating therapy // *Достижения науки и образования*. 2019. №10 (51).

27. Абдирашидова Гулноза Аблакуловна, Бакиев Шавкат Шерзодович. ЦИТОКИН БЎРОНИ ПАТОФИЗИОЛОГИЯСИ // FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA [jild: 03Nashr: 3(2024)]ISSN:2992-8915
28. Абдирашидова Гулноза Аблакуловна, Бакиев Шавкат Шерзодович. ПРОГНОСТИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СПЕКТРА ЦИТОКИНОВ И ИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ПРИ ПЕРВИЧНЫХ И РЕЦИДИВИРУЮЩИХ ЛАРИНГОТРАХЕИТАХ У ДЕТЕЙ // UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, VOLUME 2, ISSUE 9 (2024), P 87-92.
29. Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, Bakiyev Shavkat Sherzodovich, YURAK-QON TOMIR TIZIMINING BALANDLIK HOLATIDA GIPOKSIYAGA ADAPTATSIYASI PATOFIZIOLOGIYASI // ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE International scientific-online conference-2024, P 11-17.
30. Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, YURAK-QON TOMIR TIZIMINING BALANDLIK HOLATIDA GIPOKSIYAGA ADAPTATSIYASI PATOFIZIOLOGIYASI // MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE International scientific-online conference-2024, P 88-95.
31. Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, DIABETIK ATEROTROMBOZ PATOGENEZIDA YANGI JIHATLAR // FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA [jild: 03Nashr: 5 (2024)]ISSN:2992-8915, 74-76 b.
32. Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, UMUMIY XAVF OMILLARI VA MEKANIZMLARIGA EGA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI VA SARATON PATOFIZIOLOGIYASI // FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA [jild: 03Nashr: 5 (2024)]ISSN:2992-8915, 150-155 b.
33. Самиева Гулноза Уткуровна, Абдирашидова Гулноза Аблакуловна, Бакиев Шавкат Шерзодович, ЦИТОКИН БЎРОНИ ПАТОФИЗИОЛОГИЯСИГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР // Биология ва тиббиёт муаммолари 2024, №1 (151), 431-435 b.
34. GAFFAROV Ganisher Karimovich, ABDIRASHIDOVA Gulnoza Ablakulovna, & Bakiyev Shavkat Sherzodovich. (2024). TO'R PARDA KO'CHISHI PATOFIZIOLOGIYASI. FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION, 3(5), 231-236.
35. Abdirashidova Gulnoza Ablakulovna, Bakiyev Shavkat Sherzodovich, & Gaffarov Ganisher Karimovich. (2024). QANDLI DIABET I-TIPIDA SEMIRISHNING PATOFIZIOLOGIK MEKANIZMLARI. FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION, 3(5), 246-250.